

Research

Clinical Analysis of Cervical Diseases Diagnosed by Colposcopy

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Abstract: Objective: To observe and analyze the clinical application value of colposcopy in the diagnosis of cervical diseases.

Methods: The data of 1700 patients who underwent colposcopy in our hospital from June 2018 to February 2022 were retrospectively analyzed, and the examination results were analyzed and summarized. In this study, SPSS13.0 software was used for statistical analysis and summary.

Results: Among the 1700 patients who received colposcopy, 418 patients had abnormal test results. 418 patients underwent cervical biopsy pathological examination, the results showed that 227 cases had cervical intraepithelial neoplasia, 167 cases had chronic cervicitis, 15 cases had cervical condyloma, and 9 cases had cervical invasive carcinoma. The specificity, sensitivity, negative predictive value, and positive predictive value of colposcopy in the diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia were 95.63%, 97.36%, 97.04%, and 96.09%, respectively; the specificity, sensitivity, negative predictive value, and positive predictive value of diagnosing cervical invasive carcinoma were 100%, 77.78%, 99.52%, and 100%, respectively.

Conclusion: Colposcopy has important clinical value in the diagnosis of cervical diseases, especially in the diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and cervical invasive carcinoma. If combined with histopathological examination, the diagnostic accuracy will be higher. Therefore, colposcopy plays an important role in early diagnosis and treatment of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and in reducing the incidence of cervical cancer.

Keywords: colposcopy; cervical disease; clinical analysis

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Accepted: 31 July, 2023; **Published:** 20 October, 2023

How to cite this article: Ruby Singh, Chandra Rekha Issar, Sunita Ray (2023). *Clinical Analysis of Cervical Diseases Diagnosed by Colposcopy*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(7), 146-151. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10027371>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer is one of the common malignant tumors that threaten women's health. In recent years, the incidence of cervical cancer in Nepal has increased year by year, and the affected population tends to be younger[1]. Early diagnosis and treatment of cervical diseases is of great significance to the prevention of cervical cancer. The more commonly used clinical examination method is cervical smear cytology, but the diagnosis of this method is high in false negatives; with the continuous development of science and technology, colposcopy technology has also been developed rapidly, and colposcopy in the diagnosis of cervical diseases has become more and more widely recognized and used in clinical diagnosis[2]. The diagnosis of cervical diseases by colposcopy can enlarge the observation field, clearly display the

changes of cervical epithelial structure and vascular morphology, and observe the subtle lesions on the local surface of the cervix that cannot be observed by the naked eye, so as to accurately and quickly locate the lesion[3].

The concept of risk-based management means that patients are managed based on their risk of having severe precancer (cervical intraepithelial neoplasia [CIN] grade 3 positive) or cancer, rather than solely on specific test results. Correct application of these guidelines will lead to less aggressive treatment for low-risk patients and more aggressive treatment for high-risk patients. Modeling studies indicate that adopting these guidelines will be cost-effective and save lives.

Colposcopic evaluation is indicated when the presence of a malignant or premalignant lesion in the cervix, vagina, or vulva is suspected. Uncommonly, this situation may arise when an unusual cervical lesion is detected as the result of inspection of the vagina and cervix for an unrelated reason.[4]. Another specific indication is evaluation of a patient who presents with postcoital vaginal bleeding. Although this symptom is most commonly the result of vaginal or cervical trauma, postcoital bleeding is a classic symptom of cervical cancer. The most common situation arises as the result of cervical cytological screening as part of a routine health maintenance evaluation. Almost all United States cytopathology laboratories use the Bethesda System for reporting findings of cervical cytology. The version in current use is the 2001 revision.[5, 6]. Evaluation of the patient with an abnormal Pap smear has been evolving. In September 2006, a panel of experts representing 29 organizations and professional societies issued a set of consensus guidelines reflecting current understanding of the pathophysiology and natural history of cervical dysplasia[7]. Importantly, the cytologic classifications do not correspond to histologic evaluation of tissue samples, and patient management ultimately must be based on histologic diagnosis.[8] In the special case of adolescent women, who are at very low risk for epithelial cervical cancer, and in whom low-grade changes usually resolve spontaneously, colposcopy is recommended to be reserved for high-grade SIL. In the special case of pregnant women, deferring colposcopy until after delivery is reasonable unless cytologic evaluation suggests significant risk of invasive disease[9].

The detailed guidelines and rationale are available through the American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology (ASCCP) or from the following reference:

Massad LS, Einstein MH, Huh WK, et al. 2012 updated consensus guidelines for the management of abnormal cervical cancer screening tests and cancer precursors. *J Low Genit Tract Dis.* Apr 2013;17(5 Suppl 1):S1-S27.[11]

They may be summarized as follows:

- Negative for intraepithelial abnormality: These patients should continue to receive routine cytologic screening.
- ASC-H, LGSIL, HGSIL, squamous cell cancer: Because of the increased incidence of significant histologic abnormality in patients who have these diagnoses, colposcopy evaluation and biopsy of abnormal sites is recommended. In the special case of postmenopausal women, atrophic changes may result in the cytologic diagnosis of LGSIL. Managing these women similar to those with a diagnosis of ASC-US is appropriate.
- ASC-US: As with the other abnormal Papanicolaou test classification, colposcopy evaluation is an option. However, because this is the least reproducible of the cytologic categories, and because of the very low risk of invasive cancer in patients who have this diagnosis, less aggressive management strategies are also options.

These include the following:

- Repeat cytologic evaluation at 6 and 12 months
- "Reflex" testing for the presence of high-risk HPV serotypes.
- If either of these strategies results in abnormal findings, colposcopy is indicated. Should no abnormality be discerned, the patient may resume routine surveillance.

- AGC: This finding is not uncommonly associated with significant glandular or squamous cell abnormality somewhere in the lower genital tract. As neither repeat cytologic testing nor HPV testing has been found to have sufficient sensitivity to detect endocervical or endometrial abnormalities, these patients are recommended to undergo colposcopy, endocervical and endometrial evaluation, and sampling in addition to HPV testing.
- AIS, adenocarcinoma: These patients may require excisional procedures to assure adequate sampling should the above measures not be diagnostic.

In 2020, the ASCCP updated its 2012 management guidelines for abnormal cervical cancer screening results, with input from 19 stakeholder organizations, including the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG). Many of the recommendations remain the same from the previous guidelines; however, some key changes may be summarized as follows[11].

- Recommendations for colposcopy, treatment, or surveillance are based on a patient's risk of CIN 3+.
- Colposcopy can be deferred for certain patients, such as those with minor screening abnormalities indicating HPV infection with a low risk of underlying CIN 3+.
- Because HPV 16 or 18 infections pose the highest risk of CIN 3 and occult cancer, further evaluation (eg, colposcopy with biopsy) is needed even if cytology results are negative.
- If HPV 16 or 18 testing is positive, and further testing of the same sample is not available, colposcopy is the next step.

Research Methodology

General Information

From June 2018 to February 2022, a total of 1,700 patients underwent colposcopy in the Department of Gynecology of MIHS Provincial hospital, Janakpur, Nepal. The patients were 18-65 years old, with an average age of 37 years old.

Inspection method

The patient had no vaginal douching and examination within 24 hours before the examination, and no history of vaginal medication and sexual intercourse within 48 hours. Take the patient's bladder lithotomy position, use the speculum to expose the patient's cervix, place the dilator and adjust the focal length, wipe off the secretions on the surface of the cervix with a sterile cotton ball, and observe with the naked eye whether there are vegetations, bleeding, erosion and other lesions in the epithelium, transformation zone, gland opening, blood vessels and other parts. Afterwards, the acetic acid test was performed, and 3% acetic acid solution was applied to the cervix, observed for 1 min, and finally the iodine test was performed. If the cervical columnar epithelium and normal transformation zone colposcopy is negative, it indicates that the patient has chronic cervicitis or a normal cervix; if there are punctate, mosaic blood vessels and various abnormal blood vessels, white epithelium, lard-like, gyri-like structures or abnormal gland openings, the colposcopy is positive; the abnormal parts of the colposcopy image need to be biopsied.

Indications for colposcopy

Colposcopy is suitable for the following situations and symptoms [4]: (1) Gynecological general examination; (2) Cervical contact bleeding, different degrees of erosion that cannot be cured for a long time, leukoplakia, and suspicious cancer; (3) Cervical smears with Pap grade II or above, abnormal cytology, and descriptive diagnosis classification reports are atypical columnar cells, low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions, high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions, and atypical squamous cells; (4) Cervical vegetations of unknown nature; (5) Those with benign cervical diseases excluded before physical therapy; (6) Follow-up after receiving treatment for cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and cervical cancer; (7) Dynamic tracking of postpartum vaginal, cervical and vulvar lesions.

Statistical Analysis Methods

In this study, SPSS 16.0 software was used for statistical analysis and summary.

Results and discussion

Results of colposcopy and pathological diagnosis

Among the 1700 patients who received colposcopy, 1282 patients had normal examination results and 418 patients had abnormal test results. 418 patients underwent cervical biopsy pathological examination, the results showed that 227 cases had cervical intraepithelial neoplasia, 167 cases had chronic cervicitis, 15 cases had cervical condyloma, and 9 cases had cervical invasive carcinoma. The results of colposcopy diagnosis and pathological diagnosis are compared in Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison of the results of colposcopy diagnosis and pathological diagnosis

	Colposcopy diagnosis	Pathological diagnosis
Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (227)	221	6
Chronic cervicitis (167)	8	159
Cervical warts (15)	15	0
Invasive cervical carcinoma (9)	2	7

Colposcopy in the diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia

In this study, the specificity, sensitivity, negative predictive value, and positive predictive value of electronic colposcopy in the diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia were 95.63%, 97.36%, 97.04%, and 96.09%, respectively. See Table 2 for details.

Table 2 Diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia by colposcopy (example)

	Colposcopy diagnosis	Pathological diagnosis
Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia	221	6
Non-Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia	9	197

Diagnosis of invasive cervical cancer by colposcopy

In this study, the specificity, sensitivity, negative predictive value, and positive predictive value of electronic colposcopy in diagnosing invasive cervical cancer were 100%, 77.78%, 99.52%, and 100%, respectively. See Table 3 for details.

Table 3 Diagnosis of invasive cervical carcinoma by colposcopy (example)

	Colposcopy diagnosis	Pathological diagnosis
Invasive cervical carcinoma	2	7
Non-invasive carcinoma	411	0

Cervical cancer is one of the most common malignant tumors in female reproductive system diseases. According to relevant data, about 30,000 women in my country die of cervical cancer every year, seriously affecting women's life, health and safety[5]. Early diagnosis and treatment of cervical diseases is of great significance to the prevention of cervical cancer. How to diagnose and detect cervical diseases early and prevent cervical cancer has always been a topic of clinical concern. The more commonly used clinical examination method is cervical smear cytology, but the diagnosis of this method is high in false negatives; with the continuous development of science and technology, colposcopy

technology has also been developed rapidly, and colposcopy in the diagnosis of cervical diseases has become more and more widely recognized and used in clinical diagnosis[6]. Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia is a precancerous lesion of invasive cancer, which is divided into three stages: I, II, and III. The risk of developing cancer in the third stage is 15%, 30%, and 45%, respectively[7]. A small number of II patients may also develop cancer directly. Early detection and timely treatment of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia can prevent it from developing into cancer. At present, the diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia is mainly based on cytology, and colposcopy is performed for patients with abnormal cytological examination[8]. However, due to the high false negative rate of cytological examination, cases of misdiagnosis and misdiagnosis occur from time to time, delaying the best treatment time for patients and causing serious consequences[9]; however, colposcopy can enlarge the observation field, clearly display the structure of cervical epithelium and vascular morphology changes, observe subtle lesions on the local surface of the cervix that cannot be observed by naked eyes, help doctors accurately and quickly locate the lesion, reduce the false positive rate, achieve early detection and early diagnosis, and reduce the possibility of cancer[10].

In this study, a total of 1700 patients received colposcopy examination, of which 1282 patients had normal examination results and 418 patients had abnormal test results. 481 patients underwent cervical biopsy pathological examination, the results showed that 227 cases had cervical intraepithelial neoplasia, 167 cases had chronic cervicitis, 15 cases had cervical condyloma, and 9 cases had cervical invasive carcinoma. The specificity, sensitivity, negative predictive value, and positive predictive value of electronic colposcopy in the diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia in this group are all over 95%, which shows that electronic colposcopy has a high accuracy rate in detecting cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and has important clinical value. On the other hand, the specificity, sensitivity, negative predictive value, and positive predictive value of electronic colposcopy in diagnosing invasive cervical cancer are 100%, 77.78%, 99.52%, and 100%, respectively, indicating that it may cause misdiagnosis and misdiagnosis of invasive cervical cancer, and cannot accurately diagnose the condition of such patients. Colposcopy is easy to operate, does not cause trauma to the patient, and can be repeated multiple times. When the inspection is abnormal, pathological biopsy can be selectively performed on the lesion, reducing the blindness of pathological biopsy and improving the inspection efficiency. The diagnostic accuracy of colposcopy is also higher than any previous diagnostic method, especially for patients with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia, early detection and treatment can reduce the possibility of canceration, which has important clinical value and is worthy of clinical recommendation.

Conclusion

Colposcopy has important clinical value in the diagnosis of cervical diseases, especially in the diagnosis of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and cervical invasive carcinoma. If combined with histopathological examination, the diagnostic accuracy will be higher. Therefore, colposcopy plays an important role in early diagnosis and treatment of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and in reducing the incidence of cervical cancer.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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